

Awareness About Medicinal Application Of Cerium Oxide Nanoparticles Among Dental Students

Research Article

Dhanraj Ganapathy^{1*}, Martina Catherine²

¹Professor & Head of Department, Department of Prosthodontics, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Chennai, India.

²Tutor, Department of Prosthodontics, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Chennai, India.

Abstract

Introduction: Cerium Oxide (CeO₂) NPs, among other NPs, have been widely used because to their unique surface chemistry, high stability, and biocompatibility. Sensors, cells, catalysis, therapeutics agents, drug delivery careers, and anti-parasitic ointments are all made with it. Antimicrobial, anti-cancer, anti-larvicidal, photo-catalysis, and antioxidant therapies have all been documented so far using green produced CeO₂ NPs.

Aim: This survey was conducted for assessing the awareness about medicinal application of Cerium oxide nanoparticles amongst dental students.

Materials and Method: A cross-section research was conducted with a self-administered questionnaire containing ten questions distributed amongst 100 dental students. The questionnaire assessed the awareness about Cerium oxide nanoparticles therapy in medical applications, their anti-oxidant properties, anti-bacterial properties applications, anti-neurodegenerative properties applications, enzyme mimicking properties and biosensing properties. The responses were recorded and analysed.

Results: 23% of the respondents were aware of the medicinal applications of Cerium oxide nanoparticles. 19 % were aware of anti-oxidant properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles, 17 % were aware of anti-bacterial properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles, 15 % were aware of anti-neurodegenerative properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles, 14% were aware of enzyme mimicking properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles and, 10 % were aware of biosensing properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles.

Conclusion: There is limited awareness amongst dental students about use of Cerium oxide nanoparticles therapy in medical applications. Enhanced awareness initiatives and dental educational programmes together with increased importance for curriculum improvements that further promote knowledge and awareness of Cerium oxide nanoparticles therapy.

Keywords: Awareness; Cerium Oxide; Nanoparticles; Students; Medicinal.

Introduction

Nanotechnology has sparked widespread interest in every aspect of science and technology, and it is now regarded as one of the most promising study areas. It can be used in a variety of fields, including electronics, imaging, industry, and healthcare. It has mostly been used in healthcare for illness diagnosis, therapy, delivery, and formulations of innovative medications. It makes use of nanoparticles, which are small structures with a size range of 1–100 nm (NPs). These nanoscale entities have unique physicochemical features and have been used in physics, biology, and chemistry research [1].

Cerium Oxide (CeO₂) NPs, among other NPs, have been widely used because to their unique surface chemistry, high stability, and biocompatibility. Sensors, cells, catalysis, therapeutics agents, drug delivery careers, and anti-parasitic ointments are all made with it. Antimicrobial, anti-cancer, anti-larvicidal, photo-catalysis, and antioxidant therapies have all been documented so far using green produced CeO₂ NPs [2]. Antimicrobial potential is undoubtedly the most exploited among other biomedical applications. CeO₂ NPs have previously been shown to have antimicrobial properties via a variety of ways. CeO₂ NPs, on the other hand, destroy microorganisms by causing an overabundance of reactive oxygen

***Corresponding Author:**

Dhanraj Ganapathy,
Professor & Head of Department, Department of Prosthodontics, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Chennai, India.
Tel: 9841504523
E-mail: dhanrajmganapathy@yahoo.co.in

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species in cells. However, more research is needed to completely understand the precise mechanism of action [3, 4]. Our research experience has prompted us in pursuing this research [5-16]. This survey was conducted for assessing the awareness about medicinal application of Cerium oxide nanoparticles amongst dental students.

Materials and Methods

A cross-section research was conducted with a self-administered questionnaire containing ten questions distributed amongst 100 dental students. The questionnaire assessed the awareness about Cerium oxide nanoparticles therapy in medical applications, their anti-oxidant properties, anti-bacterial properties applications, anti-neurodegenerative properties applications, enzyme mimicking properties and biosensing properties. The responses were recorded and analysed.

Results

23% of the respondents were aware of the medicinal applica-

tions of Cerium oxide nanoparticles (Fig 1). 19 % were aware of anti-oxidant properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles (Fig 2), 17 % were aware of anti-bacterial properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles (Fig 3), 15 % were aware of anti-neurodegenerative properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles (Fig 4), 14% were aware of enzyme mimicking properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles (Fig 5) and, 10 % were aware of biosensing properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles (Fig 6).

Discussion

The unique property of CeO₂-NPs that makes them distinct from other antioxidants is their ability to self-regenerate their surface. Thus, one oxidant dose can work for a long time before being cleared from the body.⁷ Accordingly, various kinds of CeO₂-NPs have been synthesized in order to target the Achilles' heel of any oxidative stress-associated diseases. Investigating previous literature on ceria NPs demonstrated that different synthesis methods could provide cerium oxide NPs with various catalytic and physicochemical properties that could contribute to antioxidant or prooxidant properties [17].

Figure 1. Awareness of the medicinal applications of Cerium oxide nanoparticles.

Figure 2. Awareness of the anti-oxidant properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles.

Figure 3. Awareness of anti-bacterial properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles.

Figure 4. Awareness of anti-neurodegenerative properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles.

Figure 5. Awareness of enzyme mimicking properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles.

Figure 6. Awareness of biosensing properties of Cerium oxide nanoparticles.

Energy-dependent, clathrin-mediated, and caveolae-mediated endocytic mechanisms allow CeO₂-NP to enter cells. Singh *et al.* discovered it in mitochondria, lysosomes, and the endoplasmic reticulum, as well as the cytoplasm and nucleus. Given cerium oxide's radical-scavenging characteristics and extensive cellular distribution, a CeO₂-NP is anticipated to operate as a cellular antioxidant in different compartments of the cell, providing protection from a variety of oxidant injuries [18].

Several studies have reported CeO₂-NPs' antibacterial activity and demonstrated their considerable suppression of both gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria. CeO₂-NPs with particle sizes greater than 20 nm are thought to have antibacterial characteristics [19, 20]. Furthermore, the antibacterial effects of the highest percentage of surface Ce³⁺ of NP are consistent with many observations [21].

CeO₂-NP therapy, which removes or prevents ROS generation and impacts different important locations in brain cells or central nervous tissue, is a useful therapy for neurodegenerative illnesses. CeO₂-NPs have been shown to alter directly or indirectly, the signal transduction pathways involved in neuronal death and neuroprotection by reducing ROS generation. Cerium oxide NPs, for example, have been shown to activate neuronal survival in a human Alzheimer's disease model via altering the brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) pathway. BDNF is a protein that plays a role in neuronal survival signaling pathways [22].

CeO₂-NPs have a unique feature that could cause angiogenesis *in vivo*. Angiogenesis is the physiological process by which pre-existing blood vessels give rise to new ones. CeO₂-NPs, in particular, cause angiogenesis via altering gene regulation by modifying the intracellular oxygen environment and endogenously stabilising hypoxia inducing factor 1. CeO₂-NPs are also more catalytically active in regulating intracellular oxygen because of their high surface area, higher Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺ ratio, and tiny size, which leads to a more robust induction of angiogenesis [23].

CeO₂-NPs have been used to create a variety of biosensors, including electrochemical, fluorometric, and colorimetric sensors,

which are briefly addressed here. For the first time, the catalytic activity of cerium oxide NP was used to create a very sensitive biosensor. Synthesized electrochemical biosensors based on cerium oxide NPs were found to be effective tools for detecting H₂O₂ in as little as 1 mM of water in a study [24]. Interfacing H₂O₂ with inorganic NPs has resulted in the production of a number of nanozymes with catalase or peroxidase-like activity. *Lin et al.*, recently published a fluorometric sensing device based on DNA/CeO₂-NP for very sensitive detection of H₂O₂ [25].

CeO₂-NPs are forms of powerful artificial oxidase enzymes capable of mimicking catalase and SOD and peroxidase-like activities. *Tian et al.*, used a nanostructure-based enzyme-linked immunosorbent test to take advantage of CeO₂-NPs' peroxidase-like activity for breast cancer cell identification (ELISA). The primary antibody against a breast cancer biomarker (CA15-3) was coated on the ELISA plate in the developed system, and the second antibody was directly attached on the surface of CeO₂-NPs via electrostatic forces. When cancer cells are present, the primary antibody can capture them, and the secondary antibody-conjugated CeO₂-NPs can connect to them, causing H₂O₂ oxidation and colour change [26].

Pirmohamed et al., gave the first study on CeO₂-NPs' catalase mimicking activity [27]. CeO₂-NPs' catalytic activity has recently been used in a variety of biomedical applications. *Akhtar et al.*, found that CeO₂-NPs' catalase activity increased intracellular glutathione (GSH) in cells challenged with H₂O₂, shielding cells from oxidative damage [28]. Given the importance of GSH in cell growth and division, carcinogen metabolism, and DNA protection from oxidative damage, CeO₂-NPs' ability to increase intracellular GSH levels is a major breakthrough in medical biology. Ceria was examined for its superoxide dismutase-like activity, and researchers produced a stable and biocompatible artificial enzyme system based on CeO₂-NPs that had strong ROS scavenging activity over time. They created a biocompatible CeO₂-NP encapsulated ceria-albumin nanoparticle (BCNP) capable of decreasing intracellular ROS. The BCNPs protected the cells from oxidant-mediated apoptosis by preserving their antioxidant defence mechanism [29].

Conclusion

There is limited awareness amongst dental students about use of Cerium oxide nanoparticles therapy in medical applications. Enhanced awareness initiatives and dental educational programmes together with increased importance for curriculum improvements that further promote knowledge and awareness of Cerium oxide nanoparticles therapy.

References

- [1]. Nadeem M, Khan R, Afridi K, Nadhman A, Ullah S, Faisal S, Mabood ZU, Hano C, Abbasi BH. Green Synthesis of Cerium Oxide Nanoparticles (CeO₂ NPs) and Their Antimicrobial Applications: A Review. *Int J Nanomedicine*. 2020 Aug 11;15:5951-5961. Pubmed PMID: 32848398.
- [2]. Maqbool Q, Nazar M, Naz S, Hussain T, Jabeen N, Kausar R, Anwaar S, Abbas F, Jan T. Antimicrobial potential of green synthesized CeO₂ nanoparticles from *Olea europaea* leaf extract. *Int J Nanomedicine*. 2016 Oct 4;11:5015-5025. Pubmed PMID: 27785011.
- [3]. Elahi B, Mirzaee M, Darroudi M, Oskuee RK, Sadri K, Amiri MS. Preparation of cerium oxide nanoparticles in *Salvia Macrosiphon Boiss* seeds extract and investigation of their photo-catalytic activities. *Ceramics International*. 2019 Mar 1;45(4):4790-7.
- [4]. Rajeshkumar S, Naik P. Synthesis and biomedical applications of cerium oxide nanoparticles—a review. *Biotechnology Reports*. 2018 Mar 1;17:1-5.
- [5]. Hemalatha R, Ganapathy D. Disinfection of Dental Impression- A Current Overview. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. 2016 Jul;8(7):661-4.
- [6]. Ramya G, Pandurangan K, Ganapathy D. Correlation between anterior crowding and bruxism-related parafunctional habits. *Drug Invention Today*. 2019 Oct 15;12(10).
- [7]. Anjum AS, Ganapathy D, Kumar K. Knowledge of the awareness of dentists on the management of burn injuries on the face. *Drug Invention Today*. 2019 Sep 1;11(9).
- [8]. Inchara R, Ganapathy D, Kumar PK. Preference of antibiotics in pediatric dentistry. *Drug Invent Today*. 2019 Jun 15;11:1495-8.
- [9]. Philip JM, Ganapathy DM, Ariga P. Comparative evaluation of tensile bond strength of a polyvinyl acetate-based resilient liner following various denture base surface pre-treatment methods and immersion in artificial salivary medium: An in vitro study. *Contemp Clin Dent*. 2012 Jul;3(3):298-301. Pubmed PMID: 23293485.
- [10]. Gupta A, Dhanraj M, Sivagami G. Implant surface modification: review of literature. *The Internet Journal of Dental Science*. 2009;7(1):10.
- [11]. Indhulekha V, Ganapathy D, Jain AR. Knowledge and awareness on biomedical waste management among students of four dental colleges in Chennai, India. *Drug Invention Today*. 2018 Dec 1;10(12):32-41.
- [12]. Mohamed Usman JA, Ayappan A, Ganapathy D, Nasir NN. Oromaxillary prosthetic rehabilitation of a maxillectomy patient using a magnet retained two-piece hollow bulb definitive obturator; a clinical report. *Case Rep Dent*. 2013;2013:190180. PMID: 23533823.
- [13]. Ganapathy DM, Joseph S, Ariga P, Selvaraj A. Evaluation of the influence of blood glucose level on oral candidal colonization in complete denture wearers with Type-II Diabetes Mellitus: An in vivo Study. *Dent Res J (Isfahan)*. 2013 Jan;10(1):87-92. Pubmed PMID: 23878569.
- [14]. Menon A, Ganapathy DM, Mallikarjuna AV. Factors that influence the colour stability of composite resins. *Drug Invention Today*. 2019 Mar 1;11(3).
- [15]. Dhanraj G, Rajeshkumar S. Anticariogenic Effect of Selenium Nanoparticles Synthesized Using *Brassica oleracea*. *Journal of Nanomaterials*. 2021 Jul 10;2021.
- [16]. Ganapathy D, Department of Prosthodontics, Saveetha Dental College, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, – C, India. Nanobiotechnology in combating CoVid-19 [Internet]. Vol. 16, *Bioinformation*. 2020. p. 828–30. Available from:
- [17]. Estevez AY, Erlichman JS. Cerium oxide nanoparticles for the treatment of neurological oxidative stress diseases. In *Oxidative Stress: Diagnostics, Prevention, and Therapy 2011* (pp. 255-288). American Chemical Society.
- [18]. Singh S, Kumar A, Karakoti A, Seal S, Self WT. Unveiling the mechanism of uptake and sub-cellular distribution of cerium oxide nanoparticles. *Mol Biosyst*. 2010 Oct;6(10):1813-20. Epub 2010 Aug 9. PMID: 20697616.
- [19]. Kannan SK, Sundrarajan M. A green approach for the synthesis of a cerium oxide nanoparticle: characterization and antibacterial activity. *International Journal of Nanoscience*. 2014 Jun 7;13(03):1450018.
- [20]. Dhall A, Self W. Cerium Oxide Nanoparticles: A Brief Review of Their Synthesis Methods and Biomedical Applications. *Antioxidants (Basel)* [Internet]. 2018 Jul 24;7(8). Available from:
- [21]. Pulido-Reyes G, Rodea-Palomares I, Das S, Sakthivel TS, Leganes F, Rosal R, Seal S, Fernández-Piñas F. Untangling the biological effects of cerium oxide nanoparticles: the role of surface valence states. *Sci Rep*. 2015 Oct 22;5:15613. Pubmed PMID: 26489858.
- [22]. D'Angelo B, Santucci S, Benedetti E, Di Loreto S, Phani RA, Falone S, Amicarelli F, Ceru MP, Cimmini A. Cerium oxide nanoparticles trigger neuronal survival in a human Alzheimer disease model by modulating BDNF pathway. *Current Nanoscience*. 2009 May 1;5(2):167-76.
- [23]. Das S, Singh S, Dowding JM, Oommen S, Kumar A, Sayle TX, Saraf S, Patra CR, Vlahakis NE, Sayle DC, Self WT, Seal S. The induction of angiogenesis by cerium oxide nanoparticles through the modulation of oxygen in intracellular environments. *Biomaterials*. 2012 Nov;33(31):7746-55. Pubmed PMID: 22858004.
- [24]. Pooja D, Kumar P, Singh P, Patil S, editors. *Sensors in water pollutants monitoring: role of material*. New York: Springer; 2020.
- [25]. Liu B, Sun Z, Huang PJ, Liu J. Hydrogen peroxide displacing DNA from nanoceria: mechanism and detection of glucose in serum. *J Am Chem Soc*. 2015 Jan 28;137(3):1290-5. Pubmed PMID: 25574932.
- [26]. Tian Z, Li J, Zhang Z, Gao W, Zhou X, Qu Y. Highly sensitive and robust peroxidase-like activity of porous nanorods of ceria and their application for breast cancer detection. *Biomaterials*. 2015 Aug;59:116-24. Pubmed PMID: 25968461.
- [27]. Pirmohamed T, Dowding JM, Singh S, Wasserman B, Heckert E, Karakoti AS, King JE, Seal S, Self WT. Nanoceria exhibit redox state-dependent catalase mimetic activity. *Chem Commun (Camb)*. 2010 Apr 28;46(16):2736-8. PMID: 20369166.
- [28]. Akhtar MJ, Ahamed M, Alhadlaq HA, Khan MAM, Alrokayan SA. Glutathione replenishing potential of CeO₂ nanoparticles in human breast and fibrosarcoma cells. *J Colloid Interface Sci*. 2015 Sep 1;453:21-27. Pubmed PMID: 25965428.
- [29]. Bhushan B, Gopinath P. Antioxidant nanozyme: a facile synthesis and evaluation of the reactive oxygen species scavenging potential of nanoceria encapsulated albumin nanoparticles. *J Mater Chem B*. 2015 Jun 28;3(24):4843-4852. Pubmed PMID: 32262673.